

The Limits of Temporal Representation

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Abstract

This paper argues for a new way of approaching metaphysical problems of time by reexamining the concept of time through the lens of the representational theory of mind and Kantian epistemology. As an example of such problems, it examines the historical debate over whether time is discrete or continuous by drawing parallels between Zeno's paradoxes and Kant's antinomies. I argue that there are good reasons to treat certain properties of time as projections of the mind, supported by insights from both cognitive science and phenomenology. Building on this foundation, I introduce the term *specious event* to designate what exists in our representational world as ontological constituents. I further argue that examining different forms of representation reveals a hierarchical structure in the contents of the world, allowing a clear distinction between three categories of representation: first-level, second-level, and higher-level representations. From this perspective, moments of time are shown to be higher-level representations; they are not constituents of the

world but interpretive tools projected onto it. The question "Is time continuous or discrete?" is therefore a category mistake, reflecting the limits of our representational framework rather than a genuine metaphysical property of time.

Keywords: *Philosophy of Time, Temporal Representation, Projectivism, Specious Present, Event, Antinomies, Kant, Zeno's Paradoxes*

Introduction

The question of whether time is continuous or composed of imperceptibly small discrete parts has long perplexed thinkers. On the one hand, time is experienced as continuous; on the other hand, thinking of time as an infinitely divisible substance is hard to conceptualize. This tension is not a product of modern physics alone (for example with limiting scales such as the Planck time), but has its origins in Presocratic philosophy. This paper argues that this ancient dilemma and its recurring modern paradoxes arise from a category error: the confusion of abstract conceptual tools with the constituents of reality. From the perspective of Kantian transcendental idealism, treating time as a mind-independent substance or a *time-in-itself* fails to account for the epistemological gap between human representations and the represented reality itself. By analyzing the concept of *atomic time* from a representational standpoint, I propose that time is best understood as a structural feature of representation. The paper first clarifies the structure of our representational world and how time as a

representation fits in. It will then propose a model of the represented world, considering structures of time perception. On a representational account of time, our reality consists of specious events, and the supposed ‘moments’ of time are not constituents of it, but abstract relational markers that cannot, in themselves, compose a coherent representation of the world.

To see how this ancient dilemma has generally been framed, it is necessary to understand Zeno’s paradoxes. Zeno of Elea argued that, if time consists of distinct instants, motion and change become impossible, a problem famously shown in his *Arrow Paradox* as reported in Aristotle’s *Physics* (VI.9, 239b5–7, 239b30). Yet the opposing view appears no less problematic: If time is continuous, that means infinite potential subdivisions, illustrated in Zeno’s *Achilles and the Tortoise Paradox* (VI.9, 239b15–25). Thus, Zeno’s inquiries into time generate a deeper level of difficulty; that is, given these two paradoxes of Zeno, by exercising reason, we can accept neither time is continuous nor that it consists of discrete instants. Considering there seems to be no middle position (time is partly continuous, partly discrete), the results of these 2 paradoxes contradict each other.

These contradictions illustrated by Zeno’s paradoxes resemble what Kant later describes as *antinomies*. Antinomy is a contradiction between two conclusions of reason, which seem equally justified. It is “...*conflict of laws of pure reason.*” (*Critique of Pure Reason*, A407). Kant uses these

antinomies to illustrate the shortcomings of using pure reason in the field of metaphysics. When reason attempts to inquire about things beyond our experience, such as mind-independent time, *time-in-itself*, it leads to unsolvable contradictions. Kant’s resolution of this problem views time as *transcendentally ideal*. That means time is a necessary form of human intuition; it is not a thing out there in the noumenal world.

Kant’s own second antinomy shows this same problematic structure with a striking parallel to Zeno’s dilemma. Its thesis argues that every composite substance is made up of simple, indivisible parts; its antithesis argues that no composite thing is made up of simple parts, and nothing simple exists in the world. This conflict over the composition of reality from simple atoms versus infinite divisibility is the metaphysical counterpart to the temporal dilemma of discrete instants versus continuous flow. For Kant, both sides of this antinomy, like Zeno’s paradoxes, arise from the same mistake; that is, applying the categories of the understanding (like wholeness and part) to the world as a thing-in-itself, beyond the conditions of possible experience.

This view challenges other metaphysical inquiries into the nature of time, such as McTaggart’s (1908) arguments for the unreality of time. From the standpoint of transcendental idealism, it is no surprise that metaphysical properties attributed to time beyond experience, like A-Theory and B-Theory of time, encounter theoretical difficulties; not necessarily because time is wholly

mind-dependent, but because time is fundamental to our experience, such that it cannot coherently be conceptualized in abstraction from the conditions of possible experience. As Rukgaber (2010) explains, “Rather than agreeing with McTaggart that time is unreal, Kant claims that time is the ground and structure of what is real” (p.182). On this Kantian reading, inquiries ranging from Zeno’s paradoxes to McTaggart’s arguments for the impossibility of time, like Kant’s antinomies, reveal only the limits of human understanding when time is conceived as existing independently of our representations.

Building on Kantian insights while developing a distinct representational framework of temporal experience, I will argue that these paradoxes are not genuine puzzles about the nature of time itself. In fact, they only reflect our incorrect metaphysical framing. The dilemma of continuity versus discreteness dissolves once understood that it is a result of misapplication of our conceptual tools to a transcendent reality to which we lack epistemic access. Instead, these paradoxes only show the limits of what can be meaningfully said about time beyond the subjective conditions of experience.

The Projection of Time

Although our everyday experience of time appears straightforward, the philosophical debates around it are remarkably intricate. It is often assumed that the properties of the A-Theory of time are fundamental to human perception of time, most notably *temporal passage* and *privileged present*. Temporal passage is defined as events elapsing by becoming present and then becoming past. By looking at this

definition alone, this notion seems unproblematic since it aligns closely with pre-theoretic intuitions. Moreover, it has been argued that this feeling of passage is so self-evident that it suggests temporal passage is an objective property of time itself, independent of the mind (Norton, 2010). However, this argument has been widely contested. Some philosophers, such as Power (2021), question whether our phenomenal experience actually includes any genuine sense of passage at all. Others, including Le Poidevin (2007), argue that even if we do experience something resembling passage, it cannot correspond to an objective property of time itself, but only to the mind’s representational mode. From this projectionist perspective, the apparent movement of time does not show the nature of time-in-itself, but the structure of our temporal representation of events. Thus, the assumption that temporal passage is an objective feature of time is far from secure.

According to the *Projectivist* view of time, the feeling of passage is not a direct perception of an external temporal flow, but rather, it is a result of the mind’s interpretive process. There is a fundamental structure to experience; it is not merely a passive perceiving of the external world. The mind actively organizes perceptual input in accordance with this structure, which shapes how reality appears to us. The feeling of passage, for instance in the experience of listening to music, does not merely consist in perception of the present note followed by the succession of other notes as they become present. Instead, it is a unified experience of a sequence of notes, forming a

melody. This unique feeling arises from the mind's conjunction of present perception with very recent memories. This provides a clear example of projection: we do not simply register sensory inputs but actively construct a world with a certain temporal structure. Le Poidevin (2007) writes:

“The datum of experience, that we experience motion, is ... no mere passive reception of an objective phenomenon, but one that arises, in part, from the active interpretation of the mind. It is, at least in some cases, a projection.”

(Le Poidevin 2007, p. 93)

A more radical view rejects the very idea that temporal passage is part of human experience. This view, defended by Power (2021), claims that what we directly perceive is not the flow or passage of time, but merely *change in things*. Our primary experience, according to Power, consists of sensing change and variation, for example objects moving, sounds fading, or lights dimming. However, such experiences do not entail that time itself is flowing. On this account, we do not even experience temporal passage at all, since the mere impression of “things changing” is not enough, for genuine passage would require that *events* themselves undergo change. Referring to the experience of temporal flow, Power writes:

“Yet, no matter how this experience is explained, it is not as immediate an experience as the immediately perceived change. This change in events themselves, or in the present in relation to these events, is not a kind that anyone can have as present. It is of a past event becoming more past.”

(Power 2021, p. 168)

This position leaves no place for temporal passage within experience itself, except as a conceptual projection onto the world. However, one might object: “If there is no experience of temporal passage, why do so many people report having one?” Power's view denies not only the objective passage of external time but also the existence of any immediate subjective experience of such passage. The answer lies not in perception itself but in the way our conception of time is generated from perceptual and cognitive processes. Although raw perception does not include a sense of passage, our interpretation of phenomenological data gives rise to higher-level concepts and beliefs that depend on the mind's representational capacities. These representations need not correspond either to external reality as it is in itself or to the content of immediate experience. As evolutionary beings, our cognitive faculties produce representations not to mirror reality as it truly is, but to promote adaptive success (see Papineau 1987). If the belief in temporal passage offers practical and evolutionary advantages, and it is plausible that it does, then it is not a mystery that such a belief is widespread, even without any corresponding experiential datum. Yet the exact mechanisms that cause our belief in passage are undoubtedly complex and should be explained by referring to psychological and neurological structures, especially memory. A detailed account of these mechanisms is beyond the scope of this paper; see Mellor (1981, 1995) and Dennett (1991) for further discussion.

We do not have a dedicated sense organ for time as we do for vision or smell. If, as the projectivist view holds, temporal passage is not a fundamental part of our direct experience but rather a mental projection, then the notion of passage must be constructed from experienced events and the mind's interpretive processes. Once temporal passage is removed from our account of time, other allegedly *experiential properties* of A-theoretic time lose coherence: the “now” cannot move, persist, or be privileged since there is no flow of the present moments. Hence, if temporal passage is a conceptual projection, not an object of experience, then it follows naturally that the temporal structure of experience itself must be understood representationally. This conclusion raises a further question that will guide the next stage of the inquiry: What are the structures and limits of our representational framework that generate the experience of temporality?

The World as Event

There are different abstraction layers in how we represent perceptual experiences. Seeing a cat in a tree is one thing; forming relational concepts like “on top of” or “north of” is another. The most immediate representation, emerging directly from raw perception, may be called *phenomenal* or *first-level representation*. At this level, experience is pre-individuated and non-objectual: a continuous flux of perceptual content that has not yet been carved into discrete unities. It provides the experiential field within which the world can

appear, though not yet as meaningful or conceptualized.

Second-level representations arise when stable unities are abstracted from this perceptual flux, which makes it possible to conceptualize objects and change. Although these representations are shaped by mental processes, they belong to the world as it is represented and function as its basic constituents. A cat in my field of vision as an enduring object is an example of a second-level representation. By contrast, concepts like “on top of” are neither in our raw phenomenal representation nor in my world as an object. Unlike first and second-level representations, higher-level representations serve as tools for organizing and interpreting experience rather than as contents of the world itself. These levels of representation can be summarized as follows:

- I. First-level Representations: Pre-objectual raw sensory content. In Kantian terms, it corresponds to the *matter of intuition*.
- II. Second-level Representations: Objectual and event-like unities abstracted from phenomenal content. World-constituting and can be *pointed to* within experience (e.g., a melody, a cat standing in my field of vision).
- III. Higher-level Representations: Conceptual, propositional, and relational structures, not constituents of the world but interpretive tools (e.g., “on top of”, “before”).

Here, it is important to distinguish between different *modes of representation* and different

levels of representation. It is doubtful that any theory developed to account for perceptual representation can straightforwardly ground mental representations or thoughts as well. While some philosophers (McDowell, 1994) have maintained that perceptual experiences and beliefs share a common kind of content, a more compelling account treats perceptual representation as differing from thought, in virtue of the nature of its content. Perceptual experience represents the world through distinct sensory modes such as seeing and hearing, each of which presents items as standing in certain relations. The representational world thus consists of harmony across these different modes.

On the other hand, different levels of representations differ in their nature or format. While second-level representations are world-constituting and directly available within experience (pointable elements of the world), higher-level representations do not introduce new constituents into the world. Rather, they articulate, in propositional form, what is already given at a more basic experiential level. It is at this propositional level, Wittgenstein famously claimed, “The world is the totality of facts, not of things.” That is, the world consists of states of affairs involving things in relation, not of isolated objects. For example, seeing a cat on a mat is not merely registering ‘cat’ and ‘mat’ separately; it is the immediate representation of the relational fact ‘the cat is on the mat’ as a unified content of experience. It is important to note that Wittgenstein is characterizing the logical form under which the

world can be *described* in thought and language, not the structure of perceptual experience itself.

But there is a critical divergence. Wittgenstein’s logical facts are static; the perceptual world, however, is not given as a static totality of facts at all. We don’t have a snapshot of facts about the world in the present. What we call the “present moment” is not a cross-section like an image; rather, it is an experience that contains succession within itself. This notion is known as the *specious present*. The specious present explains why we have the perceived changes that seem to be happening *now*. We see the trees swaying directly instead of their frozen positions; we hear our name as a single utterance instead of discrete sounds of individual letters. Bergson’s account of the lived time (*la durée*) draws a similar picture. To illustrate how we experience time, he writes:

“When we listen to a melody, we have the purest impression of succession we could possibly have, — an impression as far removed as possible from that of simultaneity, — and yet it is the very continuity of the melody and the impossibility of breaking it up which make that impression upon us.”

(Bergson 2007, 124)

Following Bergson and advocates of the specious present, our perception should be understood as *temporally extended*, that is, as having a duration. If the present is not a point in time but a temporal field, then it is the container within which the events occur. It is within this field that the world is given to us. We don’t have direct access to the

future or past except insofar as they are represented within the present. In this sense, the extent of my present determines the extent of my world. Whatever is represented as perceptually or conceptually is represented in the present, and the events we perceive, we perceive in the present. The present is, therefore, the entirety of the experienced reality. This is not to say that the past and future are unreal, but rather that there is an epistemic gap between my world and other times. The past and future exist within the present as designs. Memory does not retrieve the representations from the past; it retrieves them within the present. Similarly, our anticipation of the future also occurs within the present.

If the content of our representations is intrinsically durational, then it cannot be exhaustively described as a set of atemporal facts. This suggests that, rather than a totality of facts, the world is best understood as a totality of what I will call “*specious events*.” Specious events are durational, dynamic facts in the world as we represent them. “Hearing the sound of rain” or “Seeing an apple standing” as they are experienced in the specious present, can be everyday examples of these events. They are “specious” not because they are illusory, but because they are content of the world within the specious present. These dynamical events include both the factual structure and the duration. Since specious events are objectual and carved out of the flux of raw perception, they differ fundamentally from higher-level representations. Unlike conceptual relations and logical forms, specious events belong to the represented world itself. They

are second-level representations that are constituents of the world, not merely interpretive tools. In this sense, specious events are in the world.

The present cannot have boundaries, just as our field of vision does not have boundaries. I might believe that my field of vision does not encompass everything, still, I cannot perceive its boundaries. To perceive boundaries, I also need to perceive what lies beyond them; that is, outside of them. As Wittgenstein puts it, “The subject does not belong to the world: rather, it is a limit of the world.” (*Tractatus*, 5.632), the subject cannot draw the boundary of its world from the inside. Likewise, I may believe that the present moment does not encompass all of time (past and future), but to draw its boundary, I would have to be (or know about) outside it. However, this is impossible since the present moment is all I have. The difference between the past, future and the present is that past and future are represented within the present as temporal designs, whereas the present itself is the total field in which anything can be given. A specious event is, then, an event experienced in the present. Its duration, however, can only be determined retrospectively: while a specious event is being represented in the world, it encompasses all the experienced reality without borders. Its beginning and end become available only through memory.

This retrospective articulation becomes especially clear in linguistic representation. Let us consider the sentence “Bird is on a branch (at the present)”.

While as an atemporal fact it might be correct, it is not an accurate depiction of the world. The world consists of specious events, not static facts. So instead, “Bird is landing on a branch,” or “Bird is persisting on the branch,” captures a continuous profile of the perceptual content with both factual relations and irreducible temporal extent, even though it is not possible to assess the duration within experience. This raises a further question: If specious events are the correct depictions of the world, why do we have atemporal facts as our concepts? After all, we do not experience the world as atemporal bits. What, then, are the properties of atemporal designs and in what way do they differ from the designs of the world itself (if they differ at all)? Above all, what is *moment*?

Figure 1. *Two modes of representing the same perceptual situation.*

Problem of Moment

If the world is composed of inherently durational specious events, then the notion of a durationless “moment” functions only as a higher-level conceptual tool. That is, moments are useful idealizations imposed on durational content, not the content of the world itself. Just like “north of” and “on top of”, moment is a conceptual tool; a logical

form that plays a role inside our representational world rather than being an element of it. While the abstractions like “north of” and “earlier than” are directional markers, which means they represent the spatial and temporal ordering and relations, a moment is a point marker. The most fitting spatial analogue to the moment, in this sense, would be the geometric point: a location with zero volume, a pure position without any spatial extensions. Similarly, a moment is a temporal location with zero duration, a pure “when” without temporal thickness. But just as nothing in the world can occupy a volumeless point, no perceptual representation can inhabit a durationless moment. Both are useful fictions in our representational schema necessary for measurement, mathematics and physics, yet equally unreal as constituents of the world we live in. Rather, they are the abstract gridlines we project retrospectively over the continuous canvas of specious events.

One might object that moments, even if not directly perceived, might still be derivable from events in the world since events are composed of such moments. If this were correct, a specious event could be atomized into the distinct moments that compose it. Similarly, some may argue that this *atom* of time might not necessarily be durationless. Therefore, the problem “How durationless moments can add up into something with duration?” can be resolved. The answer to these objections lies in the fundamental nature of the representations. Representations in the world are always grasped as complete and irreducible unities. While the number of their properties can be reduced, the

representation itself cannot be proportionally minimized or divided into identical constituent parts without losing its identity.

Consider the mental representation of a "pink elephant standing." Different people may imagine it with different details, perhaps without a trunk or in the style of a cartoon, yet these designs would still be complete and meaningful representations. What would it mean to imagine half of this thought, or two identical halves combining to form one? Such a notion is unintelligible. The same holds for specious events. As second-level representations that constitute the world, they cannot be broken into pieces. They cannot be restructured into a composite whole made of multiple parts. The idea of a real moment presupposes an impossible atomization of duration. It does not refer to anything in the world as represented, but functions solely as a conceptual tool imposed on it.

Ehrenfels describes a melody apprehended by consciousness as a "tonal Gestalt", a unified whole that is given at once, rather than as a mere sequence of isolated tones. He introduces this notion precisely to explain why a melody can remain the same even when all of its individual tones change (Ehrenfels, 1988). Gestalt theory takes this idea further to other modes of representation, supporting a strong claim of representational irreducibility. At its core, Gestaltism argues that the qualities of perceptual and conceptual wholes cannot be explained by merely summing isolated parts. A melody, a face, or an embodied event has a form that only emerges through organization as a whole.

Because the supposed parts of a representation are available only through such abstraction, they cannot serve as its ontological constituents. In this sense, representations are Gestalts for their unity is given prior to any identification of parts. Consequently, the idea of a smallest "moment-atom" from which longer stretches of experience are composed becomes unintelligible. By the same logic, a specious event functions as a temporal Gestalt. Any attempt to reduce this fluid, durationally thick experience into a sequence of static, durationless moments is to destroy the very phenomenon one seeks to explain.

In this sense, the world of representations is qualitative, not quantitative. Representational designs are not items that can be divided, counted, and recombined. This claim does not rule out the metaphysical possibility that physical time, independent of mind, might consist of time-atoms with very short durations. Yet in lived time experience, we neither sense such units nor inhabit a representational world built from them. Rather, it marks an important distinction: even if such temporal atoms exist at the level of physical theory, they play no role in the structure of lived temporal experience. This points to an epistemic gap between metaphysical time and experienced time. The structural properties of the two need not correspond, and there is no reason to expect that they should. Although the concept of a moment functions within our temporal framework, it is not a constituent of the world as experienced. It functions not as a depiction of reality but as a relational marker, a point of reference in time. I can locate

events *relative* to moments, but I cannot coherently conceive of events as being built from them.

Consequently, the representational world is not composed of discrete instants or identical atoms. The world as represented does not contain dimensionless moments; rather, moments function solely as conceptual tools that enhance our interaction with the world. What is in the world as constituents instead are specious events. Specious events fill the horizon of the world in the *present*; they exhaust what can be meaningfully said about the temporal structure of the experienced world. Whether time-in-itself is continuous or not is not an answerable question since we lack access to the noumenal world. At best, this transcendent time differs radically from our conception; at worst, it may not exist independently of mind at all. While physical theories may posit discrete or quantized structures for time, there is no reason to expect such structures to map to lived or represented time. The representational world is not built out of whatever entities physical theory posits at its most fundamental level. Our knowledge ends with the structure of our own representations.

Conclusion

The apparent paradox of whether time is continuous or discrete, at its core, is not a problem of the mind-independent time-in-itself, but about the limits of our representation of it. From Zeno's paradoxes to Kant's first antinomy, reason falls into contradictions when it attempts to grasp time-in-itself as a metaphysical substance with determinate intrinsic properties. Time-in-itself (if it

exists) cannot be represented, for all representation within the world already presupposes temporality as its form.

When treated as representations, what we encounter in the world is not a sequence of moments but specious events given in lived duration. The world is not given to us as temporal atoms but of temporally thick, qualitative unities that fill the *present*. The present is not a moment among others, but the horizon within which anything can be represented as real at all. What lies beyond (past or future) is not another region of time but another representation within the same horizon. Specious events are second-level representations, the constituents of the represented world, and as such they are irreducible: they cannot be reduced to momentary atoms without destroying the phenomenon they are meant to explain.

The notion of moment, therefore, is a higher-level representation; it is not a constituent of the world, but an interpretive tool, a logical form, projected onto the world. In this way, it is similar to a geometric point in space; it functions as a relational marker in the conceptual schema, not as an element of it. Consequently, the question "Is time continuous or discrete?" is revealed as a category mistake. Continuity and discreteness apply only within our conceptual projections, not to time as a condition of representation. While the represented world is composed of continuous qualitative events, the time-in-itself cannot be said to be discrete or continuous. On the projectivist account developed here, temporality is the condition under which the

world consists of events. The continuity we attribute to time is our form of representation itself, not a feature of the metaphysical substance of time. Beyond this representation of time, reason can only be silent.

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